

D2.8

Soil analysis protocols for antibiotics

Date: 15th February 2023

Version: 1

**Funded by
the European Union**

SOIL O-LIVE (Grant Agreement ID: 101091255) is funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or EIC. Neither the European Union or the European Research Executive Agency. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Deliverable 2.8 Soil analysis protocols for antibiotics

Document Information

Project title	SOIL BIODIVERSITY AND FUNCTIONALITY OF MEDITERRANEAN OLIVE GROVES
Project acronym	SOIL O-LIVE
Grant Agreement	101091255
Work package	WP2 – Soil Pollution in Mediterranean olive groves
Deliverable number and title	Deliverable 2.8 Soil analysis protocols for antibiotics
Deliverable description	Soil sampling and soil analysis protocols and quality guidelines for antibiotic and vet pollution. (T2.5)
Deliverable type	Report
Dissemination level	PU
Lead beneficiary	UJA
Due submission date	31 March 2023 (M3)
Submission date	15 February 2023

Document Author(s) and Reviewer(s)

Name	Entity	Role (author, reviewer)
Andrés Jesús Rascón López	University of Jaén	Author
Bienvenida Gilbert López	University of Jaén	Reviewer
David Moreno González	University of Jaén	Reviewer
Juan Francisco García Reyes	University of Jaén	Reviewer

Document history

Version	Date	Made by	Short Description of Changes
V1	15.02.2023	Andrés J. Rascón	Initial Report

Table of Contents

Document Information	2
Executive Summary	4
Table of Acronyms	5
1. Introduction	6
1.1 Purpose of the document	6
1.2 Definitions and abbreviations	6
2. Procedure	8
2.1 Sampling	8
2.2 Sample treatment	9
2.3 LC-MS/MS analysis	11
3. References	16
ANNEX 1: Antibiotic standards and surrogates	18
ANNEX 2: Procedural template	20
ANNEX 3: Report template	25
List of figures	
Fig 1. Exemplification of grid and sub-unit for the land division	8
Fig 2. Sampling methodology.	9
List of tables	
Table 1. Material and equipment	7
Table 2. Calibration curve	11
Table 3. Eluents	13
Table 4. Gradient for the separation	13
Table 5. Predicted MRM transitions for antibiotics	14

**Funded by
the European Union**

SOIL O-LIVE (Grant Agreement ID: 101091255) is funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or EIC. Neither the European Union or the European Research Executive Agency. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Executive Summary

D2.8 is the deliverable for task 2.5 “Assessment of antibiotics and other veterinary drug residues in olive grove soils”. This document describes the procedures required for collecting field samples and their subsequent laboratory analysis for the detection and quantification of antibiotics in the selected samples. Their identification and quantification in the pre-operational stage may contribute to the future schemes for soil restoration.

Sampling procedure is based on the protocols developed by LUCASOIL, the sampling will be carried out following a regular grid through the different olive groves. A final sample of 0.5 -1 kg is obtained. A total of 5 sub-samples should be taken to obtain the final sample. The first one must be taken from the center of the grid sub-unit (central sampling location). The other 4 sub-samples should be taken from the center spot in the shape of a cross 2 meters away in each direction. The 5 sub-samples are homogenized as one.

Samples from different types of cultivar will be collected: traditional (TD), high-density (HD), and organic (ORG), in total 52 different orchards will be sampled for their analysis. For the extraction and quantification of antibiotics in soils. The samples will undergo a microwave-assisted extraction process using a McIlvaine buffer with methanol at a pH of 3.2. Subsequently, the extracts will be subjected to solid-phase extraction to eliminate interferents from the matrix. The antibiotic profile of each sample will be determined using Ultra-High Pressure Liquid Chromatography coupled with a triple quadrupole mass spectrometer.

51 selected antibiotics (ABs) for analysis belong to nine antibiotic families: diaminopyrimidines (1 AB), quinolones (14 ABs), ionophores (2 ABs), β -lactams (10 ABs), macrolides (5 ABs), sulfonamides (11 ABs), tetracyclines (5 ABs), amphenicols (1 AB), and cephalosporins (1 AB).

The data obtained from the analyzed samples will be used to establish a profile of antibiotic presence both in different countries and across different soil management types (TD, HD, and ORG). This information will also be useful for determining the frequency with which antibiotics are detected in the samples, as well as the distribution of the compounds across different soil layers.

Table of Acronyms

Σ – Sum	MS/MS – tandem mass spectrometry
\bar{x} – Mean value	N – Number of points
AB (s) – Antibiotic (s)	Na ₂ EDTA – Ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid disodium salt dihydrate
ACN – Acetonitrile	PP – Polypropylene
HESI – Heated electrospray ionization mode	RSD – Relative standard deviation
FA – Formic Acid	S – Standard deviation
H ₃ PO ₄ – Phosphoric acid	SPE – Solid phase extraction
HPLC – High Pressure Liquid Chromatography	UAE – Ultrasound-assisted extraction
KH ₂ PO ₄ – Potassium dihydrogen phosphate	UHPLC – Ultra-High Pressure Liquid Chromatography
LODs – Limits of detection	X _i – Value in the data set
LOQs – Limits of quantification	QqQ – Triple quadrupole
ME – Matrix Effects	K – Slope of the curve
MeOH – Methanol	PP – Polypropylene
MRM – Multiple reaction monitoring	
MS – Mass spectrometry	

1. Introduction

1.1 Purpose of the document

This protocol describes the procedure for the multiresidue determination of antibiotics in soil. The procedure includes the following steps: sampling methodology, sample treatment to extract and isolate the antibiotics, and the quantification method.

During the analysis, the samples are extracted by ultrasound-assisted solid-liquid extraction. Then, the extract is cleaned up by solid phase extraction. Finally, the final extract is injected in liquid chromatography–tandem mass spectrometry.

1.2 Definitions and abbreviations

1.2.1 *Ultrasound-assisted solid-liquid extraction*

In ultrasound-assisted solid-liquid extraction (UAE), the sample is extracted using the combination of an organic liquid as an extractant and the effect of cavitation produced by the ultrasounds. This cavitation generates a huge number of small bubbles in the liquid and erodes the solid, increasing the contact between the two phases.

UAE is employed to extract analytes from solid samples by applying ultrasound radiation through an ultrasounds bath, probes, or ultrasound reactor¹. The choice between them depends on the nature of the samples and analytes. Also, extraction efficiency relies on the analytes' behaviour; not all interact the same with the sample.

To eliminate binding effects and enhance the extraction procedure, Na₂EDTA (Ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid disodium salt dihydrate) complex agent is added to the sample. Acetonitrile phosphate buffer at pH 3.2 (ACN:phosphate buffer) is used as extractant. A subrogate standard at 400 µg/kg is also added before the extraction procedure.

1.2.2 *Solid-phase extraction clean-up*

Solid-phase extraction (SPE) is a widely used technique to isolate the analytes from pre-treated extracts or directly from the samples. The main use for SPE is the concentration of analytes and the reduction of matrix effect (clean-up)².

This procedure sets the clean-up stage by combining two different SPE sorbent materials: SAX and HLB. SAX removes unwanted harmful charged humic materials from soils that could interfere with antibiotics extraction. Then, HLB act to retain the analytes.

Both SPE cartridges should be conditioned first with a combination of methanol (MeOH), ultrapure water and ACN:phosphate buffer. Sample extracts are passed through both cartridges and placed one on top of the other (SAX over HLB). They are cleaned with ultrapure water, and then only the HLB cartridge is eluted with MeOH, which is used as an extractant.

1.2.3 Antibiotics

Antibiotics are a large group of compounds from different families (e.g. fluoroquinolones, sulfonamides, beta-lactam) used to treat or prevent illnesses caused by bacteria³.

As listed in ANNEX 1, the range of antibiotics and their surrogate standards to be analysed by this protocol is wide. These compounds have been selected as they are the most used to treat cattle in the farming industry.

The methodology described in this protocol allows the determination of different families of antibiotics from soils.

1.3 Material and equipment

Table 1. Material and equipment

Sieve (2 mm)	
pH-meter	
Centrifuge	
Autoclave	
Ultrapure water HPLC-grade	
PP amber Tubes (50 mL)	
PP beakers	
Vortex	
PP Conical flasks	
PP amber vials	
Shaker	
Ultrasounds bath	
Analytical balance with 0.0001 g of precision	
Ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid disodium salt dihydrate (Na ₂ EDTA)	CAS: 6381-92-6
Formic Acid (FA)	CAS: 64-18-6
Potassium dihydrogen phosphate (KH ₂ PO ₄)	CAS: 7778-77-0
Phosphoric acid (H ₃ PO ₄)	CAS: 7664-38-2
SPE HLB cartridge (500 mg, 3 mL)	
SPE SAX cartridge (500 mg, 3 mL)	
Surrogate antibiotic standards	ANNEX 1
Antibiotic standards	ANNEX 1
Methanol (MeOH) HPLC-grade	CAS: 67-56-1
Acetonitrile (ACN) HPLC-grade	CAS: 75-05-8
N ₂ stream	Purity 99.999 %
Ultra-high-pressure liquid chromatography-tandem mass spectrometry (UHPLC-MS/MS)	Dionex Ultimate 3000 HPLC (Thermo Scientific, San José, CA USA) TSQ Endura triple quadrupole (QqQ) from Thermo Scientific (USA), fitted with a heated electrospray ionization probe (HESI)
ZORBAX ECLIPSE PLUS C18 UHPLC COLUMN	(4.6 x 150 mm, 1.8 µm)
UHPLC Software	Thermo Xcalibur Rev. 3.0.63

2. Procedure

2.1 Sampling

The initial option for the identification of sampling points is by taking samples using a regular grid with fixed dimensions (**Fig 1.**) and setting a fixed unit for selecting the sampling points (i.e. each km, randomized)⁴. The differences in the area should also be considered to capture its spatial variability.

Fig 1. Exemplification of grid and sub-unit for the land division

Following the guidelines in LUCAS SOIL⁴, the sampling methodology can be addressed as follows: A final sample of 0.5 -1 kg is selected based on the requirements of the different laboratories. A total of 5 sub-samples should be taken to obtain the final sample. The first one must be taken from the centre of the grid sub-unit (central sampling location). The other 4 sub-samples should

be taken from the centre spot in the shape of a cross 2 meters away (**Fig. 2**) in each direction. The sampling depth is fixed at 30 cm. The 5 sub-samples are homogenized as one.

Fig 2. Sampling methodology.

Finally, 0.5 kg of the mixed sample is aliquoted for its analysis.

2.2 Sample treatment

The samples should be remixed in the laboratory using mechanical movements until visually homogeneous. Three different aliquots should be taken from each sample:

- Aliquot 1 to 3: 2 g of air-dried sample for the multi-residue analysis

2.2.1 Reagents

- Surrogate antibiotics standard, 1 mg/L
- Antibiotic standards, 1 mg/L
- Na₂EDTA
- KH₂PO₄
- H₃PO₄
- ACN
- Ultrapure water HPLC-grade
- SPE SAX cartridge (500 mg, 3 mL)
- SPE HLB cartridge (500 mg, 3 mL)
- MeOH

2.2.2 Multi-residue determination of antibiotics.

- Potassium phosphate buffer solution preparation

To prepare the potassium phosphate buffer solution 27.2 g of KH_2PO_4 and 1.35 mL of H_3PO_4 should be dissolved in 1 L of ultrapure water. Then mix the solution with ACN (1:1, v/v, pH= 3.2).

- Sample treatment for antibiotic extraction

This procedure consists of UAE followed by SPE^{5,6,7}. To prevent the degradation and adsorption of some of the antibiotics, the material must be amber-colored and made from plastic (PP).

- Place the sample in a PP conical flask
- Add 400 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$ of the surrogate standards
- Place the samples for 24 h in the dark
- Add 0.4 g of Na_2EDTA ⁸
- Add 10 mL of ACN : phosphate buffer as extractant
- Shake the sample for 15 min in the agitator
- Place the sample in the ultrasonic bath for 15 min
- Transfer the sample to a 50 mL PP centrifuge tube and centrifuge for 10 min at 6 000 rpm
- Extract the supernatant and place it in a PP beaker
- Repeat the extraction steps (4 to 8) twice
- Dilute the total supernatant up to 200 mL to reduce the organic content
- Connect the SAX and HLB cartridges (SAX on the top of HLB)
- Condition the SPE cartridges with 6 mL of MeOH, 6 mL of ultrapure water and 6 mL of potassium phosphate buffer pH 3
- Pass the sample through the SPE cartridges
- Add 6 mL of ultrapure water, then dry the cartridges under vacuum for 10 min
- Remove the SAX cartridge
- Elute the analytes from the HLB cartridge with 6 mL of MeOH
- Dry with a nitrogen stream the extract and reconstitute with 1 mL of ACN. Do not elevate the temperature over 30 °C.

The supernatant is injected in LC-MS/MS using electrospray ionization mode (ESI) in positive and negative mode.

2.3 LC-MS/MS analysis

2.3.1 Analytical parameters

The analytical parameters for the methodology are characterized in terms of linearity, limits of detection (LODs) and limits of quantification (LOQs), matrix effect (ME), precision in terms of relative standard deviation (RSD) inter- and intraday and trueness.

2.3.1.1 Calibration curves, LODs and LOQs

A calibration curve is prepared each time a batch of samples is analyzed by spiking blank soil samples (as blank matrix). Soil blank samples are obtained by autoclaving soil samples, as antibiotics are degraded. To check the blank samples, they are analyzed in advance in triplicate.

An antibiotic standard working solution (1 mg/L) is used to prepare the calibration curve. Consequently, six different calibration points are prepared from 0.01 µg/kg to 1000 µg/kg.

Table 2. Calibration curve

Calibration point	Concentration (µg/kg)
P1	0.01
P2	0.1
P3	1
P4	100
P5	500
P6	1000

In those calibration points, the standard surrogate solution of 1 mg/L is added at 400 µg/kg.

LODs and LOQs are calculated as the minimum analyte concentration yielding a S/N equal to three and ten, respectively. Intra- and inter-day precision are tested for the methodology by spiking soil blank samples (n=9) at three different concentration levels 0.1, 1 and 500 µg/kg. The samples are prepared and injected in triplicate on the same day or three consecutive days, respectively.

The relative standard deviation expressed in % of peak areas should be calculated following the equation:

$$RSD = \left| \frac{S}{\bar{x}} \right| \cdot 100$$

Where:

S: standard deviation

\bar{x} : the mean value of the data set

The standard deviation should be calculated following this equation:

$$s = \sqrt{\frac{\sum_{i=1}^N (x_i - \bar{x})^2}{N - 1}}$$

Where:

S: standard deviation

Σ : sum of

X_i : value in the data set

\bar{x} : the mean value of the data set

N: number of points in the data set

2.3.2 Measurement conditions

All the vials from sample treatment and calibration curves should be placed in the UHPLC-MS/MS system and analyzed following the conditions addressed in the 2.3.4 section.

2.3.3 Results obtention

The concentration of each compound is obtained from the calibration curve equation.

If the equation is as follows:

$$\text{Area} = K \cdot [\text{compound}] + b$$

Where:

Area: area of each Compound extracted from the chromatogram

K: slope of the curve

[Compound]: compound concentration in $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$

b: intercept

The concentration is calculated using the following equation if the correlation factor is over 0.995. The concentration is calculated for each replicate, reporting the mean value of the results. The standard deviation should be added to the result.

The final concentration should be presented as follows:

$$[\text{Compound}] = \text{XX} \pm S \mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$$

To comply with LUCAS⁴ recommendations, the final concentration value can be adjusted to mg/kg by dividing the [Compound] by 1000.

2.3.4 LC-MS/MS procedure

In the case of the pretreated samples, the extracts can be injected directly, as obtained in the 2.2.2 section. In the case of calibration curves, they are also injected after following the 2.3.1 section indications.

2.3.4.1 LC conditions

This procedure is set for the Dionex Ultimate 3000 HPLC (Thermo Scientific, San José, CA USA) packed with ZORBAX ECLIPSE PLUS C18 UHPLC COLUMN (4.6 x 150 mm, 1.8 µm).

Table 3. Eluents

Eluent A	Eluent B
ACN (0.1 % FA)	Ultrapure water (0.1 % FA)

The eluents should be prepared fresh each run.

- The column oven should be set at 25 °C.
- Flow rate set at 0.4 mL/min
- Injection volume 20 µL

Table 4. Gradient for the separation

Time (min)	Eluent A (%) ACN (0.1 % FA)	Eluent B (%) Ultrapure water (0.1 % FA)	Flow (mL/min)
0	15	85	0.4
10	30	70	0.4
16	50	50	0.4
22	55	45	0.4
29	55	45	0.4
30	15	85	0.4
32	15	85	0.4

The system should be equilibrated 5 min after each run.

2.3.4.2 MS/MS settings

The TSQ Endura triple quadrupole (QqQ) from Thermo Scientific (USA), fitted with a heated electrospray ionization probe (HESI) in positive ionization mode is employed for the analysis.

The analytes are identified with chromatographic characteristics and multiple reaction monitoring (MRM) specific fragmentation. Data are processed with XCalibur software Ver. 3.0.63

The predicted MRM transitions available in the mass library NIST⁹ and Drugbank¹⁰ for each compound are the following:

Table 5. Predicted MRM transitions for antibiotics

Family	Antibiotic	CAS	Mass (m/z)	Precursor ion (m/z)	Quantification peak (m/z)	Confirmation peak (m/z)
Aminoglycosides	Gentamicin	1403-66-3	477.6	478.323	322.000	160.000
	Streptomycin	57-92-1	581.6	582.6	540.186	263.048
	Spectinomycin	1695-77-8	332.35	333.600	316.4000	133.000
	Kanamycin	8063-07-8	484.5	485.245	324.177	163.076
	Apramycin	37321-09-8	539.6	540.000	217.000	378.000
	Sisomicin	32385-11-8	447.5	448.100	430.200	322.222
	Tobramycin	32986-56-4	467.5	468.266	324.100	163.100
	Dihydrostreptomycin	19408-84-5	307.4	308.221	137.059	172.169
Diaminopyrimidines	Gentamicin Sulfate	1405-41-0	1390.728	N/A ^a	N/A	N/A
	Trimethoprim	738-70-5	290.32	291.146	123.066	261.099
Fluoroquinolones	Trimethoprim-d9	1189460-62-5	299.37	300.18	280.04	264.06
	Ciprofloxacin	85721-33-1	331.34	332.140	332.139	333.144
	Ciprofloxacin Chlorhydrate	1216659-54-9	375.8	N/A	N/A	N/A
	Difloxacin	91296-86-5	399.4	400.150	401.153	382.140
	Orbifloxacin	113617-63-3	395.4	396.153	378.142	350.148
	Enrofloxacin	93106-60-6	359.4	360.171	361.175	316.180
	Enrofloxacin-d5 hydrochloride	2733718-29-9	400.89	N/A	N/A	N/A
	Norfloxacin	70458-96-7	319.33	320.140	321.143	302.129
	Ofloxacin	82419-36-1	361.4	362.151	363.154	318.160
	Enoxacin	74011-58-8	320.320	321.135	277.146	303.124
	Danofloxacin	112398-08-0	357.4	358.158	359.161	340.147
	Levofloxacin	100986-85-4	361.4	362.150	318.16	261.103
	Marbofloxacin	115550-35-1	362.4	363.149	72.080	320.106
	Fleroxacin	79660-72-3	369.34	370.137	269.088	326.147
Sarafloxacin hydrochloride	91296-87-6	421.8	386.131	299.098	342.140	
Glycopeptides	Flumequin	42835-25-6	261.25	262.087	263.090	244.076
	Vancomycin	1404-90-6	1449.2	1121.571	1170.674	1169.688
Ionophores	Vancomycin hydrochloride	1404-93-9	1485.7	1483.002	242.080	303.097
	Lasalocid	25999-31-9	590.8	591.389	237.185	133.101
	Monensin	17090-79-8	670.9	688.463	461.326	617.404
β -Lactams	Monensin Sodium	22373-78-0	692.9	693.700	675.600	N/A
	Amoxicillin	26787-78-0	365.4	366.1118	349.085	208.042
	Amoxicillin trihydrate	61336-70-7	419.5	N/A	N/A	N/A
	Cephapirin	21593-23-7	423.5	424.063	216.033	209.038
	Cefuroxime	55268-75-2	424.4	364.000	442.000	443.000
	Penicillin G	69-57-8	334.39	335.106	160.043	56.013
	Penicillin V	87-08-1	350.4	351.101	160.043	61.724
	Oxacillin	7240-38-2	401.436	402.111	160.042	243.074
	Dicloxacillin	3116-76-5	470.3	470.033	452.000	311.000
	Dicloxacillin sodium salt monohydrate	13412-64-1	510.3	N/A	N/A	N/A
	Ampicillin	69-53-4	349.4	350.190	106.121	192.116
Lincosamides	Cefotaxime sodium salt	64485-93-4	477.5	N/A	N/A	N/A
	Ampicillin sodium salt	69-52-3	371.4	N/A	N/A	N/A
	Clindamycin	18323-44-9	425.0	N/A	N/A	N/A
	Clindamycin hydrochloride	21462-39-5	461.4	N/A	N/A	N/A
	Lincomycin	859-18-7	406.54	407.223	126.127	359.219
Macrolides	Pirlimycin	79548-73-5	411.0	411.172	270.256	393.161
	Azithromycin	83905-01-5	749.0	750.520	591.422	573.41
	Azithromycin dihydrate	117772-70-0	785.0	N/A	N/A	N/A
	Clarithromycin	81103-11-9	748.0	749.489	590.391	158.117
	Erythromycin	114-07-8	733.9	734.47	735.472	736.476
	Spiramycin	8025-81-8	843.1	843.520	174.112	142.122
Tylosin	1401-69-0	916.1	917.547	916.535	174.113	

Sulfonamides	Sulfachloropyridazine	80-32-0	284.72	285.020	156.011	108.045
	Sulfadiazine	68-35-9	250.28	251.060	108.044	92.049
	Sulfadimethoxine	73068-02-7	310.32	311.080	154.115	105.984
	Sulfadoxine	2447-57-6	310.33	311.082	156.011	108.046
	Sulfamethoxazole	723-46-6	253.28	254.059	156.011	188.081
	Sufamethoxazole-(phenyl-13C6)	1196157-90-0	259.24	260.000	160.000	112.110
	Sulfamethazine	57-68-1	278.33	279.093	124.086	204.042
	Sulfamonomethoxine	1220-83-3	280.31	N/A	N/A	N/A
	Sulfapyridine	144-83-2	249.29	250.064	156.011	184.087
	Sulfathiazole	72-14-0	255.3	256.020	212.978	186.981
	Sulfisoxazole	127-69-5	267.31	268.075	156.011	113.071
Amprolium	137-88-2	278.78	279.137	N/A	N/A	
Tetracyclines	Chlortetracycline	57-62-5	478.9	479.000	462.000	446.000
	Doxycycline	564-25-0	444.4	445.160	428.133	212.785
	Doxycycline hydrochloride	10592-13-9	480.9	N/A	N/A	N/A
	Tetracycline	60-54-8	444.4	445.160	427.150	410.123
	Tetracycline hydrochloride	64-75-5	480.9	481.271	466.04	453.09
	Methacycline hydrochloride	3963-95-9	478.9	N/A	N/A	N/A
	Oxytetracycline	79-57-2	460.4	461.155	426.117	337.069
Amphenicols	Oxytetracycline hydrochloride	2058-46-0	496.9	N/A	N/A	N/A
	Chloramphenicol	56-75-7	323.13	323.019	274.998	165.066
	Thiamphenicol	15318-45-3	356.2	356.012	307.990	309.987
	Azidamfenicol	13838-08-9	295.25	296.099	292.198	280.197
	Florfenicol	73231-34-2	358.2	358.002	339.997	246.342
Aminocoumarin	Florfenicol-d3	2213400-85-0	361.2	N/A	N/A	N/A
	Novobiocin	303-81-1	612.6	613.239	218.104	614.248
Cephalosporin	Novobiocin sodium salt	1476-53-5	634.6	N/A	N/A	N/A
	Cephapirin	21593-23-7	423.5	424.063	216.033	209.038
Streptogramin	Cefazolin	25953-19-9	454.5	455.037	323.058	324.060
	Virginiamycin	23152-29-6	1349.50	N/A	N/A	N/A
Coccidiostat	Pristinamycin	270076-60-3	1349.5	N/A	N/A	N/A
	Nicarbazin	330-95-0	426.4	427.123	N/A	N/A

^aN/A: not available

The collision energy and MRM transitions should be adjusted empirically for each compound.

3. References

- ¹ Tadeo, J. L., Sánchez-Brunete, C., Albero, B., & García-Valcárcel, A. I. (2010). Application of ultrasound-assisted extraction to the determination of contaminants in food and soil samples. In *Journal of Chromatography A* (Vol. 1217, Issue 16, pp. 2415–2440). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chroma.2009.11.066>
- ² Poole, C. F. (2003). New trends in solid-phase extraction. In *TrAC - Trends in Analytical Chemistry* (Vol. 22, Issue 6, pp. 362–373). Elsevier. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0165-9936\(03\)00605-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0165-9936(03)00605-8)
- ³ Hutchings, M., Truman, A., & Wilkinson, B. (2019). Antibiotics: past, present and future. In *Current Opinion in Microbiology* (Vol. 51, pp. 72–80). Elsevier Ltd. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mib.2019.10.008>
- ⁴ Fernandez-Ugalde, O; Scarpa, S; Orgiazzi, A.; Panagos, P.; Van Liedekerke, M; Marechal A. & Jones, A. LUCAS 2018 Soil Module. Presentation of dataset and results, EUR 31144 EN, Publications Office of the European Union, Luxembourg. 2022, ISBN 978-92-76-54832-4, doi:10.2760/215013, JRC129926
- ⁵ Hu, W., Ma, L., Guo, C., Sha, J., Zhu, X., & Wang, Y. (2012). Simultaneous extraction and determination of fluoroquinolones, tetracyclines and sulfonamides antibiotics in soils using optimized solid phase extraction chromatography-tandem mass spectrometry. *International Journal of Environmental Analytical Chemistry*, 92(6), 698–713. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03067319.2010.520122>
- ⁶ Pan, M., & Chu, L. M. (2016). Adsorption and degradation of five selected antibiotics in agricultural soil. *Science of the Total Environment*, 545–546, 48–56. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2015.12.040>
- ⁷ Salvia, M. V., Vulliet, E., Wiest, L., Baudot, R., & Cren-Olivé, C. (2012). Development of a multi-residue method using acetonitrile-based extraction followed by liquid chromatography-tandem mass spectrometry for the analysis of steroids and veterinary and human drugs at trace levels in soil. *Journal of Chromatography A*, 1245, 122–133. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chroma.2012.05.034>
- ⁸ Berendsen, B. J. A., Lahr, J., Nibbeling, C., Jansen, L. J. M., Bongers, I. E. A., Wipfler, E. L., & van de Schans, M. G. M. (2018). The persistence of a broad range of antibiotics during calve, pig and broiler manure storage. *Chemosphere*, 204, 267–276. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chemosphere.2018.04.042>
- ⁹ National Institute of Standards and Technology OR National Bureau of Standards, U.S. Department of Commerce. (2023). *NIST Mass Spectrometry Data Center*, accessed 14 February 2023, <https://chemdata.nist.gov>
- ¹⁰ Wishart, D. S., Feunang, Y. D., Guo, A. C., Lo, E. J., Marcu, A., Grant, J. R., Sajed, T., Johnson, D., Li, C., Sayeeda, Z., Assempour, N., Iynkkaran, I., Liu, Y., Maclejewski, A., Gale, N., Wilson, A., Chin, L., Cummings, R., Le, Di., ... Wilson, M. (2018). DrugBank 5.0: A major update to the DrugBank

database for 2018. *Nucleic Acids Research*, 46(D1), D1074–D1082.
<https://doi.org/10.1093/nar/gkx1037>

ANNEX 1: Antibiotic standards and surrogates.

Table 1. Antibiotic standards and surrogates

Family	Antibiotic	CAS	Surrogate standard	CAS			
Aminoglycosides	Gentamicin	1403-66-3	Gentamicin Sulfate	1405-41-0			
	Streptomycin	57-92-1					
	Spectinomycin	1695-77-8					
	Kanamycin	8063-07-8					
	Apramycin	37321-09-8					
	Sisomicin	32385-11-8					
	Tobramycin	32986-56-4					
	Dihydrostreptomycin	19408-84-5					
Diaminopyrimidines	Trimethoprim	738-70-5	Trimethoprim-d9	1189460-62-5			
Fluoroquinolones	Ciprofloxacin	85721-33-1	Ciprofloxacin Chlorhydrate	1216659-54-9			
	Difloxacin	91296-86-5					
	Orbifloxacin	113617-63-3					
		Enrofloxacin	93106-60-6	Enrofloxacin-d5 hydrochloride	2733718-29-9		
		Norfloxacin	70458-96-7				
		Ofloxacin	82419-36-1				
		Enoxacin	74011-58-8				
		Danofloxacin	112398-08-0				
		Levofloxacin	100986-85-4				
		Marbofloxacin	115550-35-1				
		Fleroxacin	79660-72-3				
			Sarafloxacin hydrochloride	91296-87-6			
	Flumequin	42835-25-6					
Glycopeptides	Vancomycin	1404-90-6	Vancomycin hydrochloride	1404-93-9			
Ionophores	Lasalocid	25999-31-9					
	Monensin	17090-79-8	Monensin Sodium	22373-78-0			
β -Lactams	Amoxicillin	26787-78-0	Amoxicillin trihydrate	61336-70-7			
	Cephapirin	21593-23-7					
	Cefuroxime	55268-75-2					
	Penicillin G	69-57-8					
	Penicillin V	87-08-1					
	Oxacillin	7240-38-2					
		Dicloxacillin	3116-76-5	Dicloxacillin sodium salt monohydrate	13412-64-1		
				Cefotaxime sodium salt			
	Ampicillin	69-53-4	Ampicillin sodium salt	69-52-3			
Lincosamides	Clindamycin	18323-44-9	Clindamycin hydrochloride	21462-39-5			
	Lincomycin	859-18-7					
	Pirlimycin	79548-73-5					
Macrolides	Azithromycin	83905-01-5	Azithromycin dihydrate	117772-70-0			
	Clarithromycin	81103-11-9					
	Erythromycin	114-07-8					
	Spiramycin	8025-81-8					
	Tylosin	1401-69-0					
Sulfonamides	Sulfachloropyridazine	80-32-0					
	Sulfadiazine	68-35-9					
	Sulfadimethoxine	73068-02-7					
	Sulfadoxine	2447-57-6					
		Sulfamethoxazole			723-46-6	Sufamethoxazole-(phenyl-13C6)	1196157-90-0
		Sulfamethazine			57-68-1		
		Sulfamonomethoxine			1220-83-3		
		Sulfapyridine			144-83-2		
		sulfathiazole			72-14-0		
		Sulfisoxazole			127-69-5		
	Amprolium	137-88-2					
Tetracyclines	Chlortetracycline	57-62-5					

D2.8 Soil analysis protocols for antibiotics
Project SOIL O-LIVE (ID: 101091255)

	Doxycycline	564-25-0	Doxycycline hydrochloride	10592-13-9
	Tetracycline	60-54-8	Tetracycline hydrochloride	N/A
	Methacycline hydrochloride	3963-95-9		
	Oxytetracycline	79-57-2	Oxytetracycline hydrochloride	2058-46-0
Amphenicols	Chloramphenicol	56-75-7		
	Thiamphenicol	15318-45-3		
	Azidamfenicol	13838-08-9		
	Florfenicol	73231-34-2	Florfenicol-d3	2213400-85-0
Aminocoumarin	Novobiocin	303-81-1	Novobiocin sodium salt	56677-21-5
Cephalosporin	Cephapirin	21593-23-7		
	Cefazolin	25953-19-9		
Streptogramin	Virginiamycin	23152-29-6		
	Pristinamycin	270076-60-3		
Cocciostat	Nicarbazin	330-95-0		

ANNEX 2: Procedural template

Project:

Sample information:

Samples:

Date of process:

Performed by:

Samples			
Sample name <i>Code XXXX</i>	Replicate 1 <i>Code XXXX</i>	Replicate 2 <i>Code XXXX</i>	Replicate 3 <i>Code XXXX</i>
Sample name <i>Code XXXX</i>	Replicate 1 <i>Code XXXX</i>	Replicate 2 <i>Code XXXX</i>	Replicate 3 <i>Code XXXX</i>
Sample name <i>Code XXXX</i>	Replicate 1 <i>Code XXXX</i>	Replicate 2 <i>Code XXXX</i>	Replicate 3 <i>Code XXXX</i>
Sample name <i>Code XXXX</i>	Replicate 1 <i>Code XXXX</i>	Replicate 2 <i>Code XXXX</i>	Replicate 3 <i>Code XXXX</i>
Sample name <i>Code XXXX</i>	Replicate 1 <i>Code XXXX</i>	Replicate 2 <i>Code XXXX</i>	Replicate 3 <i>Code XXXX</i>
Sample name <i>Code XXXX</i>	Replicate 1 <i>Code XXXX</i>	Replicate 2 <i>Code XXXX</i>	Replicate 3 <i>Code XXXX</i>
Sample name <i>Code XXXX</i>	Replicate 1 <i>Code XXXX</i>	Replicate 2 <i>Code XXXX</i>	Replicate 3 <i>Code XXXX</i>

1. Sample treatment

The samples should be remixed in the laboratory using mechanical movements until visually homogeneous. Three different aliquots should be taken from each sample:

- Aliquot 1 to 3: 2 g of air-dried sample for the multi-residue analysis

1.1 Reagents

- Surrogate antibiotics standard, 1 mg/L
- Antibiotic standards, 1 mg/L
- Na₂EDTA
- KH₂PO₄
- H₃PO₄
- ACN
- Ultrapure water HPLC-Grade
- SPE SAX cartridge (500 mg, 3 mL)
- SPE HLB cartridge (500 mg, 3 mL)
- MeOH

1.2 Multi-residue determination of antibiotics

- Potassium phosphate buffer solution preparation

To prepare the potassium phosphate buffer solution, 27.2 g of KH₂PO₄ and 1.35 mL of H₃PO₄ should be dissolved in 1 L of ultrapure water. Then mix the solution with ACN (1:1, v/v, pH= 3.2).

This procedure consists of UAE followed by SPE^{5,6,7}. To prevent the degradation and adsorption of some of the antibiotics, the material must be amber-colored and made from plastic (PP).

1. Place the sample in a PP conical flask
2. Add 400 µg/kg of the surrogate standards
3. Place the samples for 24 h in the dark
4. Add 0.4 g of Na₂EDTA⁸
5. Add 10 mL of ACN : phosphate buffer as extractant
6. Shake the sample for 15 min in the agitator
7. Place the sample in the ultrasonic bath for 15 min

8. Transfer the sample to a 50 mL PP centrifuge tube and centrifuge for 10 min at 6 000 rpm
9. Extract the supernatant and place it in a PP beaker
10. Repeat the extraction steps (4 to 8) twice
11. Dilute the total supernatant up to 200 mL to reduce the organic content
12. Connect the SAX and HLB cartridges (SAX on the top of HLB)
13. Condition the SPE cartridges with 6 mL of MeOH, 6 mL of ultrapure water and 6 mL of potassium phosphate buffer pH 3
14. Pass the sample through the SPE cartridges
15. Add 6 mL of ultrapure water, then dry the cartridges under vacuum for 10 min. Remove the SAX cartridge
16. Elute the analytes from the HLB cartridge with 6 mL of MeOH
17. Dry with a nitrogen stream the extract and reconstitute with 1 mL of ACN. Do not elevate the temperature over 30 °C.

The supernatant is injected in LC-MS/MS using electrospray ionization mode (ESI) in positive mode.

2. LC-MS/MS analysis

2.1 Calibration curves

A calibration curve is prepared each time a batch of samples is analyzed by spiking blank soil samples (as blank matrix). Soil blank sample is obtained by autoclaving soil as antibiotics are degraded in the process, to check the blank samples, they are analyzed in advance by triplicate.

An antibiotic standard working solution (1 mg/L) is used to prepare the calibration curve. Consequently, six different calibration points are prepared from 0.01 µg/kg to 1000 µg/kg.

Calibration point	Concentration (µg/kg)
P1	0.01
P2	0.1
P3	1
P4	100
P5	500
P6	1000

In those calibration points, the standard surrogate solution of 1 mg/L is added at 400 µg/kg.

2.2 LC conditions

This procedure is set for the Dionex Ultimate 3000 HPLC (Thermo Scientific, San José, CA USA) packed with ZORBAX ECLIPSE PLUS C18 UHPLC COLUMN (4.6 x 150 mm, 1.8 µm).

Eluents:

Eluent A	Eluent B
ACN (0.1 % FA)	Ultrapure water (0.1 % FA)

The eluents should be prepared fresh each run.

- The column oven should be set at 25 °C.
- Flow rate set at 0.4 mL/min
- Injection volume 20 µL

The gradient programme for the separation is as follows:

Time (min)	Eluent A (%) ACN (0.1 % FA)	Eluent B (%) Ultrapure water (0.1 % FA)	Flow (mL/min)
0	15	85	0.4
10	30	70	0.4
16	50	50	0.4
22	55	45	0.4
29	55	45	0.4
30	15	85	0.4
32	15	85	0.4

The system should be equilibrated 5 min after each run.

2.3 MS/MS settings

The TSQ Endura triple quadrupole (QqQ) from Thermo Scientific (USA), fitted with a heated electrospray ionization probe (HESI) in positive ionization mode is employed for the analysis.

The analytes are identified with chromatographic characteristics and multiple reaction monitoring (MRM) specific fragmentation. Data are processed with XCalibur software Ver. 3.0.63

ANNEX 3: Report template

Report XXXXXX/2023

No of pages: XXXX

Reception date:

Starting date:

Finishing date:

Report elaborated by:

Test

Multiresidue method for the determination of antibiotics in soil

Samples

1. Sample name
 - a. Sample code

Test Method

Multiresidue method for the determination of antibiotics in soil

Results

Multiresidue method for the determination of antibiotics in soil

Starting date: XX/XX/XXXX

Finishing date: XX/XX/XXXX

Table 1

Sample		Antibiotics			
		Number of antibiotics detected	Highest concentration (mg/kg)	Sum (mg/kg)	
Sample name					
Code XXXX					
Antibiotic analysis					
<i>Sample XXXX</i>					
Retention time (min)	Name	Mass	CAS-No.	Concentration (mg/kg)	Comments

Sum of identified substances					
Remarks					

Table 2

Sample	Antibiotics		
	Number of antibiotics detected	Highest concentration (mg/kg)	Sum (mg/kg)
Sample name <i>Code XXXX</i>			
Sample name			

<i>Code XXXX</i>			
Sample name			
<i>Code XXXX</i>			
Sample name			
<i>Code XXXX</i>			